

“GEORG BÜHLER (1837-1898)”
by
J. Jolly¹
(Translated from German into English)

By
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The disturbing mishap which took away Privy Councilor Bühler on 8th April 1898 in the middle of the freshest activity from the science and his relations and friends, has also deprived the “Grundriss der Indo-Arischen Philologie und Altertumskunde” its founder and editor. When in what follows, an attempt is undertaken, to give an outline of the scientific activity and personality of the famous Sanskritist to the readers of the “Grundriss”, in connection with his so widely ramified, epoch-making activity towards many directions, an attempt which can be described as a bold venture that only in the absence of his own letter-records about Bühler, an excuse is found. For the early days and for the time of his stay in India (1863 up to 1880), there exists an excellent “Vita” reaching up to 1878, which he wrote in every year at the suggestion of his priest of the brother-in-law Frick in Zürich for the family of his fiancée and later wife. I let this autobiography which was placed at my disposal by the above mentioned gentleman in the most kind manner, follow with a few abridgement (almost only in bibliographical passages) and some supplementary notes to which the material particularly were taken by him out of which the interesting letters of Bühler from India to him entrusted to me by Nöldeke in the most friendly manner.

“Georg (Joh.) Bühler, son of Pastor Johann G. Bühler, born at Borstel near Nienburg, Prov. Hannover, on 19th July 1837, trained through private instruction, attended the upper fifth and sixth of the City-Gymnasium at Hannover from the Easter 1852-1855, where H. L. Ahrens, the author of the famous work on the Greek Dialects, and the

¹ Published as [I] *GRUNDRISS DER INDO-ARISCHEN PHILOGIE UND ALTERTUMSKUNDE* (Encyclopaedia of Indo-Aryan Research) Established by G. Bühler, Continued by F. Kielhorn, Vol. I, Part A

famous Grammarian R. Kühner imparted education in the classical languages.¹ In the Easter of 1855 with the certificate of maturity released, he was immatriculated as stud. Theol. And phil. in Göttingen and studied classical philology under K. F. Herrmann, F. Schneidewin, E. v. Leutsch, H. Sauppe and E. Curtius, Sanskrit and Zend under Th. Benfey, German Philology under Leo Meyer, [2] Persian and Armenian under H. v. Ewald, Arabic under Wüstenfeld, Archaeology under F. Wiesler and Philosophy under H. Lotze, and became member of philological as well as of archaeological and later, of the pedagogical seminar.² In the summer-semester of 1858 he graduated himself in Oriental languages and Archaeology while his dissertation dealt with the suffix *tes* from the field of the Greek grammar.³ In the autumn of the same year he went towards Paris to use the Sanskrit-manuscripts of a library there;⁴ and in the middle of 1859, towards London for the same purpose. The stay in England continued up to October 1862. This time was used mainly for the study of the Vedic MSS of India Office and of Bodleian Library Oxford as well as of the Comparative mythology, and in it the inspiring intimacy with Max Müller, Th. Goldstücker, C. Lottner and Whitley Stokes was of not less value. At that time, B. officiated first as a private teacher and later (since May 1861) as assistant of the librarian of the queen in Windsor Castle. Literarily, he was collaborator in Benfey's Journal "Orient und Occident" and delivered also a lecture

¹ One may perhaps assume that particularly, Ahrens, always highly honoured by him, had encouraged B. to his later studies, as even Ahrens himself expresses, in the school-censures in an appreciating manner, and with increasing warmth about the progress of this student, whom he gave warning at the time of learning the Gymnasium only to protect himself from over-working, yet six weeks before his death, B. had participated in a Jubilee of his Gymnasium in Hannover.

² Bühler always considered Benfey as his own teacher in Göttingen. B.'s doctoral dissertation, his edition of *Pāiyalacchī* which he let be printed at his own cost in the Felicitation volume in Benfey's 50 years' Jubilee of doctorate, in 1878, and the *Daśakumārac.* are dedicated to Benfey and his first works mostly connected with the direction of Benfey's studies appeared in his "Orient u. Occident". Also to his co-students with Benfey, Th. Nöldeke and J. Budenz (later Professor of ancient Linguistics in Budapest, 1892), with whom he discussed and disputed on the comparative grammar in an unending manner, he had to thank for many suggestions. An intimate, life-long friendship bound him with the famous Semitist Nöldeke who was around one semester senior to him and to whom he was closely associated with.

³ With a lot of humor, later on in the circle of friends B. has narrated about his doctoral examination at the time of which he impressed famous Ewald, the examiner of the main subject, through a citation out of Roth's *Nirukta*.

⁴ B. procured the funds for this stay through a house-teacher's position in a prominent Russian family in Paris.

before the Philological Society of London.¹ Towards the end of 1862 B. was nominated to be the Assistant of the University-library at Göttingen and in October was emigrated towards that. There, busy with the preparations of the Habilitation (= appointment as University Lecturer), already through the mediation of Prof. Max Müller, he obtained the offer to go as Anglo-Sanskrit Professor in the Sanskrit College, Banaras in the month of November. Before the negotiations on this position could be led to the end, similarly through Max Müller, in December an invitation came from the Director of Public Instruction to accept the position of a Professor of Oriental Languages in the Elphinstone College in Mumbai.² To this [3] call, B. obeyed immediately and already on the 10th of February 1863 he arrived in Mumbai. There the position for oriental languages was only newly created, so was very much to connect with activity of organization of the instruction, of the procurement of a library and of the most necessary manuscripts. Along with these works and the lectures on Sanskrit, Prakrit, and language-comparison, a part of Latin studies was also to be undertaken. In that year B. was nominated for the Fellow of the Bombay University and member of the Bombay Branch Royal Asiatic Society. In the University he had to work as examiner in Sanskrit, Latin and Greek;³ and before the Asiatic Society, he delivered

¹ "On the Hindu God Parjanya" 1859 (printed in the Transactions); "On the Hindu God Savitr and his relation to the Greek Poesidon", 1861; "On Schleicher's Compendium of Comparative Grammar, with a discussion of Certain Greek Phonetics", 1862. A work on "Helena und die Dioskuren" remained incomplete. To the "History of Ancient Sanskrit Literature" of Max Müller, he supplied the Index (cf. Preface, p. VII).

² For the actual creation of the Professorship, he had to thank Sir Alexander Grant, the then Principal of the Elphinstone College, later Director Public Instruction, in whom B. found a patron, he knew how to esteem its eminence. His gratitude [3] comes to the expression in the dedication of his *Āpastamba*-edition to Sir A. Grant "as token of his admiration and thankfulness".

³ According to his letters to Nöldeke occasionally he examined in connection with Marathi also with which he had made himself familiar quickly, and with Philosophy. Further he used the opportunity to learn Sanskrit as a living language in the communication with the Pandits, in connection with which he must "learn afresh" his Sanskrit completely as before him Haug, his the then Colleague in Pune had done. "In this part of India, still significant traditional knowledge and of Indian antiquity is available. The people divide themselves in Vedīs and Śāstrīs. The Vedīs mostly studied one Veda, i.e. they learn the text of the Samhitā to recite, without understanding it, this recitation is actual recitation half song, half reading, with a peculiar accentuation whereby the Anudāttatara and the Svarita were strongly displayed.... Besides this the people learn the Brāhmanas, Āraṇyakas, Upaniṣads, and Sūtras simply by heart, often with the commentaries, and among them those who are Yājñikas, sacrificial priests, understand at least the Sūtras very well. As against this, the Śāstrīs, learn the Prose-literature, and these are people who know very much. My Śāstrī who is not at all a very

many more lectures.¹ In the beginning of 1864 he, along with the then Registrar of the Bombay High Court, R. West, through the then Governor Sir Bartle Frete was selected to compose a Digest of Hindu Law cases along with a representation of the Indian law valid in the Bombay-Presidency, which could substitute pandits knowing law who were straight way abolished for the lower courts of justice. In the middle of the same year, the professorship of the ancient history in the Elphinstone College was assigned to him as subsidiary office on the recommendation of the New Director of Public Instruction, Sir A. Grant. Both the next years were devoted to the completion of the Indian Law² and to the collection of the manuscript-literature with reference to it, and to the publication of the smaller works from this field and to the linguistics in the [4] "Orient und Occident", Journal Royal Asiat. Society and Madras Literary Society. The work was delayed by difficult, repeated attacks of fever which had great weakness and nerve-pains as the consequence and which forced to accept the there Professorship of Sanskrit, at the time of Prof. Haug's exit from the Deccan College in

great scholar, knows the entire Pāṇini by heart, knows every verbal form, and knows whether the roots make Ātmanepada or Parasmaipada" (Letter to N. 1863). Already in the July of 1864 he knows Sanskrit "as good as English". Up to 1868, he drove from the Śāstra particularly Dharma, further Nyāya somewhat Vyākaraṇa, the Alaṅkāraśāstra in connection with the artistic poetry, particularly Kālidāsa, learnt the melodies of the several metres by heart, worked on a Sanskrit-Syntax and studied the Gṛhya-practices with a Yājñika.

¹ On Indian child-marriage, on Śākaṭāyana, on Krama, Jaṭā, Mālā and other manners of recitation of the Veda, among others.

² "I work hard on my Indian Digest of Law case with the best Dharmaśāstravid of the Presidency and already have overcome 500, approximately 1/5 cases. We speak only in Sanskrit" (Letter to N., 11th June 1864). "In order to give a brief idea on the sources of the Law, so much has been quite clear to me that all the versified works are based on the declaration of opinions – in Sūtraform – of the several Veda-schools. In connection with many, this can be now quite significantly shown e.g. in connection with, Āpastamba, Prajāpati, Manu etc. Brāhmaṇas studied the Law, firstly because [4] they occupied the positions of judges, just as they do even now, and secondly because it is a part of the Karmamīmāṃsā. Besides this source, there is a second, – the Gāthās of Law – sayings in Śloka-form which existed in a very great number, and partly originated from the Veda-schools, partly perhaps also are of other origin, belong to the people, and many are perhaps brought in form by the poets. These latter have the style of the codices brought into verses and let themselves easily be recognized in their sententious form" (11th Oct. 1864). "Every Sanskrit citation", it is said in the Preface to the "Digest", was searched by Dr. Bühler "carefully, many times even new, better suitable texts were chosen out of the multitude of the recognised Śāstras and the controversial issues were decided through the conclusions of his researches on the concerned fields of the Sanskrit-literature".

1866 temporarily.¹ The first volume of the Digest of Hindu Law, dealing with right of succession, therefore, appeared only in the beginning of 1867.² Still, before this work was published, from the Governor, Sir B. Frere, B. received permission to be able to travel in the Southern Maratha Land and the Northern Canara to investigate the Brahmanical libraries there, and to make great purchases of MSS of rare works, wherever possible. B. performed this travel in company of the Director of Pub. Instr. during the months November, December and January of 1866-67. The proceeds of MSS amounted to more than 200, and among these there were many novelties and rare works, particularly in the field of Vedic literature and Grammar. After the completion of this travel, B. returned to his old position as Professor of the Oriental Languages and of the ancient history in the Elphinstone College and continued the same up to the end of 1868. During this period, he published two numbers³ in the Bombay Sanskrit Series founded by him and Dr. Kielhorn, Superintendent of Sanskrit in the Deccan College Pune. This enterprise was begun in order to give an opportunity to the young Indian scholars to learn the methods of critical edition and to produce cheap and useable textbooks for the Bombay-Colleges. Up to 1878 somewhat twenty small volumes were published and besides both the founders, Shankar P. Pandit, Professor Ramkrishna G. Bhandarkar, Kāshināth T. Telang, Ābāji Kāthavate, all the students of the Elphinstone and Deccan College participated therein.⁴ In the year 1868, B. [5] also published a critical edition of the text of Āpastambīya Dharmasūtra for the Bombay-government⁵ and some Sanskrit-school-books for the Dept. of Public Instruction. In December 1868, B. was nominated for Acting (or

¹ Kielhorn, the Successor of Haug substituted B. in Bombay, in between.

² See under List of Writings. Besides the working on the Sanskrit-citations, B. furnished an epoch-making Introduction based on comprehensive manuscript-studies, on the sources of the Indian Law to the first volume and a supplement to the oldest Sanskrit-texts on the law succession. Already in 1867 in a Resolution the Government expressed its special thanks to the authors of the Digest.

³ See under List of Writings.

⁴ Also numerous other publications of the Indian friends of B. in the Indian Antiquary and elsewhere, prove, that his efforts to free the native scholars from the one sided studies of their Śāstras and to train them for collaboration in the Research in the Indian Antiquity were crowned with best success.

⁵ [5] Also for the law-books of Gautama, Baudhāyana, Viṣṇu, Vasiṣṭha and Nārada, B. had collected a rich manuscript-material and thought of critically editing them, entrusted, however, later (only in connection with Gautama, Stenzler, 1876 with his edition forestalled him), his materials with the liberality peculiar to him, to the young scholars for their editions of those works.

Commissioner) Education Inspector of the Northern part of the Bombay Presidency. At the same time he was commissioned (along with Kielhorn) by the Indian Government, which at this time, had begun to turn its attention more on the research of ancient libraries in India to undertake this work for the Western India.¹ The time of the inspection-travels was used for it during the winter of 1868-69 in all the big cities of the Province for making acquaintances with the learned Brāhmaṇas and possessors of libraries and for enlisting the agents who should trace out the libraries and prepare catalogues of the same. It was soon proved that the richness in libraries and books was enormous and that particularly the sects of the Jainas very much similar to the Buddhist possessed incomparable treasures of manuscripts. Thus in Khambay in two Jainalibraries over 30000 manuscripts were found, many out of which originated from the 12th or 13th centuries. The result of the investigations were so good, that after the first year over 200 ancient, mostly very beautiful MSS were purchased and catalogues prepared, which alone contained approximately 14000 titles for the Brahmanical

¹ Already, shortly after his arrival in India, B. had begun (according to his own information in ZDMG, 42, 530ff) to employ himself to a private collection of Sanskrit MSS and to preparation for the Digest, for which many unpublished law-books were necessary for him, doubled his eagerness of collection, who directed himself to original mss as to reliable transcripts which he let prepare in Madras, Benares and other cities. "I purchase MSS where I can manage them; it is, however, not easy which to preserve. The Brāhmaṇas will not easily give them to the unbelieving persons. Only the pure need or deceitful middlemen entice them away, from those. I have become passably lucky in my speculations and have preserved some valuable things." (Letter on 5th April, 1865). Thus he became successful, obviously with the sacrifice of his entire savings, already upto 1866, to bring together the greatest part of his valuable collection of 321 MSS, which he made a donation to the India Office Library in 1888 – a particularly brilliant example of his high-hearted liberality, with which he actually met at the same time every bad calumny, which could grow up for him in his later peculiarity as an official purchase of manuscripts from the private possession. At several times he handed over his remaining collection to the Berlin-library which received in all 177 MSS in 201 volumes given by him, as well as he founded a valuable collection of Indian coins in Berlin. Also in the so much successful establishment of the Search for Sanskrit MSS B. was not indirectly unconcerned. The deserving founder of the same, Wh. Stokes, at that time Secretary of the Indian Consulate in Simla, in his official report dated 6th Aug. 1868, Simla, on the Catalogisation of all the Sanskrit-MSS suggested by Pandit Rādhākṛṣṇa in Lahore, repeatedly refers to the manuscript researches of his friend B. and emphasizes that the Organization of the Search of MSS planned by him agreed completely with the operation-plan drawn up briefly by B., according to which he had collected over 200 valuable codices from a small district. According to the proposals of Stokes, the Searches for Sanskrit MSS were organized all over in India and the stately sum of 24000 Rupees was instituted in the Indian Year-Budget for it.

literature. In the [6] Spring of 1869 the second part of the Digest of Hindu Law cases, containing the division of the property of a united family along with Excuse on the right of succession of women was published.¹ For the rest, the official businesses, which were very much increased through the preparations of the new Dir. Of Publ. Instr. for a thorough reform of the Primary and Secondary education system, as well as a difficult accident prevented the publication of further scientific works. In December 1869, as a result of the accident he returned to Europe on medical leave, where the restoration of his health made him so much to produce which could not be thought of while on work. Already, before the leave was ended, he returned to India (in November 1870), to accept the position of the Educational Inspector N. D. (which in May 1872 was assigned to him definitively). During the next years, he had to dedicate himself mainly to the already begun reorganization of the education-system. In the course of the next six years, the number of schools was increased circa 800 to circa 1600, through strengthening of the seminaries (training colleges) for a better and general training of the teachers taken care of, new normal-plans for the instruction introduced and schools carefully classified, as well as care taken for detailed yearly inspection of the schools. At the same time the wages of the teachers in the secondary schools were significantly increased and opportunities were given to the teachers of primary schools to earn yearly increase (in Salary) through particularly good management.² Although the

¹ The entire work was translated in Marathi, Gujrathi and Kannad, from which High Court in Bombay the juristic trials were placed at the base and has witnessed two editions; in the third (1884) the law-historical introduction was essentially changed; thus Bühler could utilize for it, his discovery published first in 1868, on the time of composition of *Mitākṣarā*, the most important of all the Indian Law-books out of the new period.

² "My district is enormously big, greater than the entire Bavaria, and for my 5½ millions of residents, there are now somewhat more than 600 schools...primary schools, continuation-schools, Sanskrit-schools, Progymnasia, School-teachers-training-schools, Industry-schools, among others. I have to organize all these schools to watch over, to construct buildings, to give them grants and to punish. For this I have six sub-inspectors, and an office of 8 clerks and book-keepers...wages 1361 Rs (per month), rank of 1st Lieutenant...I am since 15th November upto today (12th April) on the way, and have patrolled 1100 miles and god knows how many schools inspected, and examined. I use now the opportunity to communicate with all the possible social classes intimately. A year among the people has fixed me in the holy Sanskrit-literature and -culture more easily than six years in Mumbai - Besides I continuously collect MSS or inspect libraries....As far as Veda is concerned so I consider the usual view about the nature of the *Ṛgveda*, as a kind of song book for devotion to be entirely incorrect. I believe that Indians are still correct that the hymns are just "Mantras" i.e. magical formulae which

immediate-Inspection of the Secondary Schools and Seminaries (training Schools), the general supervision of the work of the zonal inspectors in the primary-schools, as well as the general administration-work took a lot of time, still B. was able to publish in the year 1871, the second part of his edition of the Aphorisms of Āpastamba [7] on the Sacred Law, containing extracts from the Sanskrit-Commentary and an Index¹, as well as the first fascicule of the Catalogue Sanskrit MSS from Gujrath. In the year 1872 and 1873 three further fascicules of the Catalogue and a small volume in the Sanskrit-Series, No. I, the first half of his edition of the Daśakumāracarita of Daṇḍin containing critical and explanatory notes appeared. At the same time in the year 1872 the activity of editing of the Indian Antiquary, of a new Journal for Indian Antiquity, through J. Burgess in Bombay, in which Dr. B. lively participated, during the first two years with articles on Sanskrit-works newly found by him and later with the publication of Inscriptions, which were found by him in Gujrath.² Along with these works, the collection of MSS for the Indian Government progressed and in 1870/71 68 MSS, 1871/72 more than 200 MSS, 1872/73 420 MSS, 1873/74 280 MSS, 1874/75 56 MSS and 1875/77 839 MSS were purchased. The purchases in the year 1873/74 were made in the western Rājputānā, towards which B. was sent by the Indian Government for the research of ancient libraries in Jodhpur, Jesalmer, Bikaner and Bhatner. The library of Jainas in Jesalmer gave the most unexpected results and showed that there were Indian MSS of the age of more than 800 years, but yielded also two actually historical poems, out of which, one the Vikramāṅkacarita was edited in 1875 as Bo. Sanskrit Series No. XIII. The collections of the years 1875-77 originated out of Kāshmir, the eastern Rājputānā and Central India where B. made a long tour on the order of the Indian Government. This tour in Kāshmir was described in a separate fascicule of the Journal Bombay Br. R. As. Soc. Bombay, 1877.³ The proceeds consisted mainly of a great

should force the gods to the gift" (Letters to N. 1872-75). As early he learnt Marathi, now he learnt Gujrathi, so thoroughly that he was dispersed of the usual examination in the language of the land.

¹ [7] The second, based on 13 MSS edition of Āpastamba containing also a list of variants of the HiraṇyakeśiSūtra appeared in 1892-94.

² Inscription soon became B.'s favourite study, so that he designated himself with special liking as epigrapher. In inscriptions he found the sure dates miserably missing for a long time for the political and cultural history of India.

³ The important Kāshmir Report contains, besides the MSS-list, also detailed investigations on the age of the works discovered by B. and extracts from the same, B. also brought forward a lot of new material for the criticism and explanation of the Rājatarāṅgiṇī and pointed out, as Stein, in his worthy edition of this work has remarked,

number of unknown Brahmanical works from Kashmīr and an almost complete collection of the sacred literature of the Digambara (or Naked-going) Jainas. Along with the purchases for the Indian Government, B. took care, with the special permission of the latter, also for the greater collections of MSS, for the libraries of Berlin, Cambridge and Oxford, and let himself be planned to make the collected treasures accessible to his colleagues; wherewith the famous liberality of the English Government in the activity of sending off their [8] manuscripts stood to his side.¹ In the year 1877 he went again towards Europe on leave, and in 1878 gave an edition of Pāiyalacchi, the oldest Prakrit-Wörterbuch, along with Glossary and translation (Göttingen, 1878). He also undertook the translation of Āpastamba-DharmaSūtra and other ancient works on Indian Law for Prof. Max Müller's collective work, "The Sacred Books of the East".²

So far the "Vita" of 1878. After completion of his leave-time, during which he had married in Switzerland, B. along with his young wife returned back to India where he again took over his activity as Educational Inspector, on 27th May 1879, already, however, in the following year as several symptoms of liver-pains occurred, on the medical advice he arrived at the decision to apply for pension. The binding of the exerting official duties along with an extensive scientific activity had gradually become too much for his powerful constitution and amazing working power. The discharge with pension was granted to him, and it favourably happened that exactly around this time a teaching chair for Indian Philology and Archaeosophy was established in the Wiener

the way for the work still to be carried out.

¹ [8] The total number of the MSS purchased by him for the Indian Government is given by B. in ZDMG 42, 526, where he reports on his collective gain in a detailed manner, as 2876. Later B. has supplied the acquisition of Indian MSS mostly from the sphere of the Jaina-literature also for Wien and Leipzig.

² B. himself mentions following recognitions fallen to his lot up to 1878, in his "Vita": 1858 Membre de la Société Asiatique, Paris; 1871 corresponding member of the Deutsche Morgelandsche Gesellschaft and correspondent of the Institute des langues Orientales vivantes; 1872 Knight-Cross III. class of the Prussian Crown-ordens; 1876 Corresponding Member American Oriental Society; 1878 Companion of the Order of the Indian Empire; 1878 Corresponding Member of the Kaiserl. Akad. d. Wiss. in Wien and of the K. Ges. d. Wiss. in Göttingen; 1885 Officiating member of the Wiener Akademie; Honorary member of the R. Asiatic Society in London and Honorary Doctor of Laws in Edinburgh; 1887 Honorary member of the American Oriental Society and Corresp. Member of the Institut de France; 1889 K. K. Hofrat; 1890 Member of the Executive council of the D. M. G.; 1893 Corresponding Member of Petersburg Akademie; 1895 Honorary Member of Asiatic Society of Bengal; 1897 Compteur des Franz-Josef-Ordens.

University. B. was obtained for this Professorship by the Austrian Government; on 18th September 1880 he left India, passed the winter of 1880/81 on the Riviera in order to acclimatize himself again in Europe and in the Summer semester of 1881 took up his new teaching office in Vienna.

Full seventeen years B. worked in Vienna, approximately as long as he had been working in India. Now in Vienna he could fully devote himself to the scientific research unhindered by the fetters of a heterogeneous official activity, and to work in full leisure on the materials, experiences, and impressions collected in India. The teaching duties in a German university and in his own work-sphere could not take the power of the vigorous man in his forties, who had completely recovered himself again from the effects of the Indian Climate, in claim exorbitantly, so he devoted himself ardently to an [9] extensive teaching activity from the beginning. Already in January 1881 by Mentone he announced Nöldecke his intention to prepare cycles of lectures, which should extend over the most branches of the History of Indian Literature and of social life. For the beginners in Sanskrit for the winter semester 1881/82 he composed printed in the beginning only as manuscript, "Leitfaden Für den Elementarkursus des Sanskrit" (Wien, 1883), by himself in India, he introduced in the German University-teaching, his "Sanskrit Ollendorff" of the practical methods which was tested in India and was translated into English also as "Sanskrit Primer". With completely modest expectation as regards the size of his auditorium B. had gone to Wien, it however, soon became successful for him to bring together a very magnificent course of lectures. I was so surprised when he allowed me to sit and supervise a lecture in the Summer-semester of 1882, to find therein, perhaps a half hundred eager listeners who must have collectively already brought before them the first principles of Sanskrit, since they could fluently interpret Nala and Damayantī. Even people in ripe age, gymnasial professors, absolved jurists, priests, officers, one book-seller and one book-printer, many University-colleagues, also even one woman colleague were present, as he writes to Nöldecke, his listener from time to time. Gradually he educated also a number of special students who are or were active indologists in several countries; I mention Block, Cartellieri, Dahlmann, Führer, von Sehtscherbatskoi, Winternitz. Many of the above-mentioned scholars certainly came to Bühler already well-prepared or after completion of their own university-study. His lectures besides the elementary course of Sanskrit which he let in two parts in every year, according to the printed

lists consisted of: Indian Law, particularly family-law and inheritance-law, with or without explanation of *Mitākṣarā* (eight times); Indian History (twice); History of Western India (once); social and political composition of India (once); Indian Religion-history (twice); ancient Indian art (twice); history of Indian script (once); Indian Palaeography (six times); Indian Epigraphy; Aśoka-inscriptions (eleven times); epigraphical-historical exercises, interpretation of history-sources (eight times). Indian Fable-literature and *Pañcatantra* (seven times); *Daśakumāracarita* (twice); *Kādambarī* (twice); *Kirātārjunīya* (once); *Śrīharṣacarita* (twice); *Gauḍavaḥo* (once); *Kumārasāmbhava* (once); *Raghuvamśa* (thrice); Indian Drama along with explanation of *Śakuntalā* (once); *Mālavikāgnimitra* (thrice); *Vikramorvaśīya* (twice); *Mālatīmādhava* (once); explanation of philosophical works: *Tarkasaṅgraha*, *Vedāntasāra* among others (six times), *Siddhāntakaumudī* (seven times), poetics and *Kāvyaḍarśa* (thrice); Pāli, Prakrit and Gujarathi (twice each). According to the communications of a listener he also did not make it [10] easy to the beginners in anyway, examined rather a lesson of his textbook in every hour so that he completed the whole book in the course of a winter-semester and could pass over to the lectures of the *Nala*-poem and to the syntax in the summer. He also let make writing exercises e.g. to translate the fables of Aesop in to Sanskrit, stressed on this that his students should learn to write *Devanāgarī* beautifully, as he was generally particular about not many but only about clever student. Very willingly he used to read *Pañcatantra*, with advanced students, used to stimulate epigraphical exercises and in the Oriental Institute he used to have always a number of stereotype small plates in store to his listeners. For his special students no labour was too much for him and to them he himself used to offer his vacation, thus once he sat together with a listener in the Oriental Institute in the Easter-vacation two full days from the early morning upto the evening and took with him a revision of the entire Aśoka-inscriptions in *Kharoṣṭhī*-script, which adorned around the walls of the Institute. The establishment of the Oriental Institute to which two halls were allotted, was resulted out of his initiative. In the oriental museum, he held a great range of lectures on the Indian Educational System and on a journey through the Indian desert. Outwardly he worked through a wide-spread correspondence, was indefatigable in the execution of numerous inquiries reaching him, pursued the references to the German colleagues, to India and England and used to begin anew. Many important publications were not written or printed without him, many ancient

inscriptions were not excavated without him, many colleagues thanked him for their career entirely or partly.

Here is the place also of thinking about his prominent activities in the gatherings of scholars, particularly in connection with the International Congress of Orientalists, to which the Austrian Government delegated him. What a change of time of his stay in leave in Germany 1877-79 where he marked himself as a "simple administrative-officer" in the communication with the German colleagues with proud modesty upto the International Congress of London onwards (1892), at which he was regularly chosen as the Vice-president of the Indian Section which was always numerously visited, and the deliberations of which he knew how to direct, frequently interrupting in the debates with equally good lot of tact and discretion as result. The visitors of Wiener Congress (1886) became thankful to his amiable hospitality for the colleagues and of interesting communication with the colleagues from India think that honouring was excellently represented. In London, even the mission to propose the vote of thanks for president of the Congress, Max Müller fell to his share. At the Wiener Philologen-Versammlung (Gathering of Philologists of Vienna) (1893), he carried out the work of President of the Oriental Section. Also in the General meetings of the Deut[11]sche Morgenlandische Gesellschaft (German Oriental Society), the Executive Council of which he belonged upto the end, he had often participated.

Out of his literary activity, which he used to dedicate to the long forenoon of the Indian early risers, while he held his lectures exclusively in the afternoons, in the Wien time mainly to be stressed as the continuation of his works in the field of the Dharmaśāstra. From the beginning he had helped his old friend Max Müller in the great enterprise of the "Sacred Books of the East". Out of his "Sacred Laws of the Āryas, Part I, Āpastamba and Gautama" (Oxf. 1879) appeared as the 2nd volume of the collection was the translation of Āpastamba which was already printed in Mumbai in big form as an annexation to his text-editing, however, still not published; he let it pulp again in favour of the "Sacred Books" and to print it newly in Oxford with a little changes and further he added to it an extraordinarily thoroughly thought over and careful introduction as the result of his summer-stay in 1878 in Switzerland, the introduction which has thrown a new light on the entire history of the Vedic Schools. For the text of Gautama he could use, along with the Stenzler's edition, a draft of the text-constitution prepared earlier in accordance with the valuable manuscripts collected by himself

in India; in the Introduction he reached the conclusion to recognize the oldest preserved work of its kind in the Smṛti of Gautama, through careful argumentation just as Stenzler did independently however, from this scholar¹. In 1897 this second volume of the "Sacred Books", first of all the volumes witnessed a second edition, for which among others, the newly obtained dates for an earlier application of the commentary of Haradatta, lying at the basis of the translation, could be utilized. The translation of Vasiṣṭha and Baudhāyana published in 1882 as 14th Volume of the "Sacred Books" also rests almost completely on the material collected by B. himself. The problem to be solved was more difficult as the law-book of Baudhāyana, at that time above all not yet edited and the text of Vasiṣṭha itself was transmitted very badly in the best manuscripts and prints and was not controllable through an ancient commentary. The high-point of B.'s contribution to the Sacred Books, however is marked by the unusually strong 25th Volume of this collection which contains his translation of the "Laws of Manu" (1886). Therein, for the translation and notes not only the seven old commentaries were used in a detailed manner, to the greatest parts again in accordance with the manuscripts collected by B. himself in India and also B.'s knowledge about modern India and of inscriptions have very much come to the place, but also in an appendix, 1. a survey particularly important for Indian jurists, on the collective quotations [12] from Manu in the medieval and modern Law books is given in English translations and 2. an index of the parallel places to Manu in other ancient Law-books, Mahābhārata, Upaniṣads and other ancient works is given. The very detailed introduction contains an enormous material for all the problems concerning the origin and history of our Manu in a clear disposition and allusive representation; B. fixes the time of composition of this famous work earlier than most of his modern predecessors.

While, in this manner, he brought his researches of twenty years in the field of History of Indian Law, to a worthy close, he stopped for no moment his epigraphical works. Thus he contributed to the monumental work of Burgess on the Cave-temples (Arch. Survey of Western India IV and V Volumes 1883), the work on cave-inscriptions with careful chronological arrangement according to the view-points laid down through Paläography. To the South-Indian Survey of Burgess he supplied the text and translation of the Aśoka-edicts in Dhauli and Jaugada. The "Indian Antiquary" produced many of his epigraphical works; I mention

¹ ZDMG, 47, 621

for example the continuations of his Valabhī, Raṭhor, and Gurjara grants; the corrected texts of Aśoka's Pillar-edicts, the researches on Nepalese History connected with works of Bhagwanlal Indrāji and Bendall. As the "Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum" established by A. Cunningham found its continuation in the *Epigraphia Indica* of Archaeological Survey, B. became one of the most industrious collaborators in this big collective work. The first part, a grand quarto volume, which reached its close in 1892 contains, under 46 epigraphical articles not less than 20 originating from B. thereunder among others, the newly discovered Aśoka-edict of Shahabgarhi, the inscription excavated by Führer in Mathurā, the "Inscription of horse-dealers" of the year 882/3 a. d., the one which is new found in Cintra in Portugal, Praśasti of 1287 a. d. originating from an Indian temple, and a South Indian Pallava-inscription in Prakrit, the discussion on which instigated B. to the formation of the remarkable theory that Prakrit was the official language of the Indian Kings and only gradually through the influence of Brāhmaṇas and in a form modified by them, out of a local dialect of the north, Sanskrit became the language of the educated in entire India. How important it was also e.g. and what justified satisfaction it gave to B. that in 1888 he discovered a document of gift of the famous king Harṣa of Saṃvat 25=621 or 632 a. d. containing valuable details on a copperplate which partly confirmed Bāṇa and partly supplemented Hiuen Tsiang's information on the history of this powerful king. In 1894 a second similar document of the king Harṣa was discovered and was deciphered by B. [13] The 2nd Volume of *Epigraphia Indica* completed in 1894 contains, among 40 epigraphical contributions, again 10 were authored by B. From the third volume onwards the work of editing passed on to B.'s earlier student Dr. Hultzsch in Madras, his own contributions were rare in the 3rd and 4th volumes, yet, however, to the 1st part of the 5th volume in 1898 he supplied two articles out of which one deals with the two edicts of Aśoka, determining the birth-place of Buddha, which Führer had excavated in Nepal in December 1896. The Aśoka-inscriptions for which new discoveries, stereotype copies, and photographs supplied him a rich augmentation in material, have really kept B. particularly busy, thus he has dealt with on that also in a series of articles, which were published in the *ZDMG* and contained multitude of new readings and explanations. One may remember e.g. his explanation which is now perhaps generally accepted, about the Rājukas of Aśoka as "Land-surveyors". Among his numerous inscriptional articles in the *W. Z.* here only his investigations on the Muthurā-inscriptions may be stressed, the significance of which

for the History of the Jainas will be clear afterwards. Among his epigraphical publications in the *Wiener Akademieschriften* (Academic writings from Vienna) the essay on the "Die Indische Inschriften und das Alter der indischen Kunstpoesie" ("The Indian Inscriptions and the age of the Indian artistic poetry") is of general interest (1890). Supported by the surely datable Gupta-Inscriptions, which Fleet had compiled, here he proved that during the first five centuries a. d. a Kāvya-literature must have existed and the Vaidarbha-style of poetry reached the recognition already before the middle of the 4th century. In connection with the uncertainty of all dates falling in the period before 600 a. d. for the history of the Indian poetry, this discovery marked a tremendous progress. The "Anzeiger der Wiener Akademie" (Journal of the Vienna Academy) in which he frequently published provisional communications on his works, contains, among others, also his interpretation of a Kharoṣṭhī-Inscription on a Greeko-Buddhist pedestal (1896) which he made paläographically plausible, that this sculpture belongs to the second century a. d., an important hint for the age of the Greeko-Buddhist art.

Burgess says that the Indian Inscriptions form, yet more than those of other countries, the actual Archive of the ancient Annals of the country; they are the contemporary witnesses of events and of men about which they report to us and their reliability makes them highly valuable for us, for the history-researchers. Along with these indisputable witnesses of the Indian past on stone and copper, the scanty remnants of the historical-biographical literature of India, contained in the Mss did not interest B. less, about which he had won entirely extraordinary merit. "With your idea, that Indians have no historical literature, you stand on obsolete stand-point", he could report to Nöldeke already in 1877. "In the last 20 years [14] five pretty considerable extensive works have been found which originate from contemporaries of the described events, four out of them have been found by me (Vikramāṅkadevacarita, Gauḍavaha, Pṛthivirājadigvijaya, Kīrtikaumudī). I am on the trace of yet more than a dozen", while Vikra. was edited by B. himself, Gauḍa. by an Indian scholar incited by him, in the Bombay Sanskrit Series, he published now in the *Wiener Akademieschriften*, detailed investigations on Arisimha's Sukṛtasamkīrtana (1889), a "praise-song on the plans or beneficial to the public enterprises of the famous minister Vāstupāla from the first half of the 13th century, by a contemporary Jaina-poet, and on the historical novel Jagaducarita by Sarvāṇanda (1892), which deals with a liberal Jaina-merchant of the 13th century, who at the time of a great famine came forward as a benefactor of his co-religionists and country-people.

Already previously (1888) with Zachariae in accordance with a London manuscript he had dealt with the Navasāhasāikacarita of Padmagupta who composed the work around the year 1000 and was a protégée of the King Sindhurāja, the father of the famous Bhoja.

Through his epigraphic and manuscript-related researches B. developed himself also into the master of Indian Paläography and reached an astonishing readiness and trustworthiness in deciding the time of composition of the undated inscriptions and manuscripts on the basis of the character of the handwriting. Thus in 1890 in a Chinese province in Kashgaria when a manuscript which subsequently was marked as Bower manuscript on the basis of its discoverer, was found, B. and Hörnle, the latter decipherer of the manuscript, simultaneously reached to the result that it must be fixed in the 5th century on the basis of the Paläographic reasons. Already, earlier, B. had led the investigation of the manuscript discovered in the monastery Horiuzi in Japan, in the *Anecdota Oxoniensia* (1884) to important Paläographical conclusions, among others, to the general principle that the inscriptional alphabets are thoroughly more ancient than the contemporary manuscript-related alphabets. His description of Paläography of 350 b. c. upto 1300 a. d. in the *Grundriss* (1896) contains a thorough compilation of his versatile Paläographical studies. His essay "On the Origin of the Indian Brāhma Alphabet", published in two editions in 1895 and 1898 is to be considered as a complement there; in it he has derived the Indian script out of a north-semitic Alphabet from the period around 800 B. C. similarly as earlier A. Weber had, with, however, much comprehensive material; further the investigation published in *W. Z.* 1895 on the origin of the Kharoṣṭhī-alphabet, the script of the north-west running towards left which he similarly led back to a semitic source still reaching back only up to the period of the first Achämenides.

At the time of his stay in Gujarath, he had frequently come into [15] contact with the sect of the Jainas which was domiciled there from the ages, respected and influential through their Kingdom there, had attended their sermons and recitations of Sacred scriptures, which are attractively narrated in his popular essay "Indische Erbauungsstunden" ("Indian Devotional Hours") (1894), and opened their almost immensurable manuscript treasure, as already mentioned, for the European knowledge. Thus he dedicated a fine study particularly language-scientific activity of the Jaina-monk Hemacandra (1889) to the destiny and the scholars deciphered the Jaina-manuscripts going back upto the first century a. d. the manuscripts which were discovered by Dr.

Burgess and then particularly by Führer in the excavations in Mathurā which were undertaken by Burgess in the charge and incited by Bühler, and therein found important corroborations to the information contained in the literature of the Jainas on the ancient Gaṇas, nun-order and corporations of laymen of the Jainas referred to the wheel and Stūpas of the Buddhists also in connection with the Jainas, proved their art in general as almost identical with the Buddhist one (1888ff); discovered a Jaina-story on the Stūpa in Mathurā (1897), worked on both the already mentioned historical Jaina-poems along with their rich religion-historical and culture-historical details and gave a lecture “über die indische Sekte der Jainas” (“On the Indian sect of the Jainas”) in the Wiener Akademie (1887), a general survey on the historical position of the same. It was also very important that B. was another prominent scholar who knew to win through care of manuscript-material and personal influence for these studies¹. Along with the proceedings only some main directions of the literary activity of B. in the Vienna time will be pointed out. It would be far crossing over the frame of this outline, to attempt a complete characterization of his numerous small, and big publications in the Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde des Morgenlandes established and edited by him in collaboration, as well as earlier in the “Österreichische Monatschrift für den Orient”, in the “Journal of the R. Asiatic Society” in London, of which he was an honorary member, in the writings of the Wiener Akademie, the “Academy”, in the “Athenaeum” and other Journals. I may here point only towards his highly gifted universality which stands out even in the period at Vienna in his literary activity as well as his activity as a university lecturer already spoken about. Thus the editor of Śākaṭāyana and of Paiyalacchi prove his fundamental thorough knowledge of grammar and lexicography newly shining in the discussion with Whitney on the reality of the roots and forms brought forward by the Indian Grammarians, in connection with which he [16] referred to some hundred untraced roots and forms in the Jātakas, Kāvyaś etc (1894), in the discussion about Yādavaprakāśa’s Vaijayantī (1887), in his “Lexicographical Notes” (1888f) and in the stimulation and guidance for the edition of the “Quellenswerke der altindischen Lexicographie” (“Source-books of the ancient Indian Lexicography”) through the Wiener Akademie (1893ff). It may be here incidentally remarked that indeed through his long stay in India he was out of connection with the further development of the linguistics in Germany,

¹ Cp. Hörnle’s Annual Address etc. 1898, 3-19 (Calc. Review April 1898, p.1ff) on the development of the Jaina-philology.

that however, later his interest for the comparative linguistics was manifested among others through the establishment of the "Indogermanische Gesellschaft" ("Indogermanical Society") in Vienna in association with Meringer (1893ff). This Gesellschaft (Society) held a meeting in the premises of the Oriental Institute, on his invitation and he never missed its meetings. In the field of Philosophy which he had promoted in India, besides through his manuscript-researches, also through the edition of the Nyāyakośa caused by him and Kielhorn, his detailed notes to the philosophical parts of Manu made the correct comprehension of the theorems essentially easy. Also to the research of the Mahābhārata he made an important contribution in his Manu, through the detailed discussion of the parallel places in both the works, and took the entire question about the origin of the great epic into the hand in his "Contributions to the History of the M." (with Kirste, 1892), where he demonstrates mainly on the basis of Kumārila's Tantravārttika in a detailed manner that already at the time of the composition of this work i.e. in the first half of the eighth century, the Epic must have been in existence essentially in its extant form. With the Purāṇas which he holds to be ancient in general, in contrast to the prevailing view, he has made himself busy among others, in the Introduction to his Āpastamba (besides also Ind. Ant. 25.323-328) and in his detailed investigation on the extracts from the Viṣṇudharmottara with Alberuni (1890), his lively interest remained already always turned towards the artistic poetry, and to the poetics standing in connection thereby in view of the historical Mahākāvya and the poetry contained in the inscriptions. One may compare particularly the already mentioned work on the inscriptions and the age of the art-poetry (1890). B. himself understood very well the good verses composed according to all the rules of the Alankāraśāstra to show *pāṇḍityam*. How the Buddhist literature interested him lively is proved, along with his epoch-making works on the Aśoka-inscriptions, particularly by his frequent allusions to the Jātakas, this in the works on Aśoka's Rājūkas (1893), among others, the inscriptional expressions (1898), on the roots of the Dhātupāṭha (1894), and on the Brāhma-Alphabet (1895); these Buddhist stories, in which he recognised the Thesaurus of the private and stately antiquity of India, formed his favourite reading for a longtime. The ancient Geography of India had made him busy particularly in the [17] interest of the Epigraphy, as he cared for leading even his listeners happily in the presence of the map of India. That he studied the ancient monuments not only as an epigraphician but also as an Archäologist, is proved e.g. by his already

mentioned investigations on the Jaina-sculptures in Mathura in which he gave even a lecture in the London Congress (1892). If he has, in his later works, apart from that of the Sūtra-literature and that in the history of Vedic Schools on which he had gained a lot of material in the inscriptions, only rarely entered, then this is concerned with not simply underestimation of the Vedas but with this that he considered it only more urgent task of the Indology, to determine the historical dates to be attained certainly, and that he emphasized willingly the difficulty and darkness of the Vedic texts which he fixed completely in general in the "prehistorical" epoch of the Indian culture, about the antiquity and originality he had very high opinion, as for example his interesting remarks on Jacobi's investigations on the age of the R̥gveda (Ind. Ant. 1894) demonstrate.

B.'s incomparable command of the entire further areas of Indology and his always growing authority made him acknowledged leader of great enterprise, which made him busy in a prominent manner in his last years of life and for the accomplishment of which he obtained leave repeatedly from his management, of the *Grundriss der Indoarischen Philologie und Altertumskunde* (Encyclopaedia of the Indo-aryan Philology and Archäosophy). Already in the seventies of years he had proposed exhaustive work on "Indian Antiquities" in English language, with Nik Trübner whom credit goes for the London publisher for the *Orientalia*, the work which should substitute the antiquated work *Indische Altertumskunde* of Lassen, was, however, stopped because of his epigraphic researches and among others the urging works in the execution of that plan. Then K. J. Trübner, the nephew of N. Trübner in Strassburg, the famous philological publisher put an offer to him at the time of the London Congress, in 1892 to deal comprehensively with the Indian Philology also in collaboration with colleagues, in the manner of the *Grundriss der germanischen und romanischen Philologie* (Encyclopaedia of the German and Roman Philology) which was published in his publication-company and which was regarded highly in the scientific world. B. promised and through the weight of his name and his international connection, collaboration to obtain colleagues not only of German and Austrian but also English, Dutch, North-American and Indian ones and thus he could already publish the prospectus in 1895, in which representing every important branch of Indian Philology through a separate monograph and in the distribution of the branches through application of the "Mārgas" with the specific Indian shade, were observed. The individual representations should appear in an irregular

sequence with separate pagination. The Paläography, the political history along [18] with the sources of history and a considerable part of the real facts had been taken over by B. himself and soon he was in a position to publish in his already mentioned representations of Paläography (1896) a masterpiece of the most laborious research along with rich tables of almost innumerable variants of ancient Indian Alphabet up to 1300 a. d. which for the so difficult a study of the inscriptions was made easily available to every Sanskritist. B. had left behind an English edition of his Paläography press ready, with preliminary studies for Geography which he intended to work upon with Dr. Steine in Lahore, and for the history of India in the pre-mohammadan times, which only an Epigraphist of the first rank like him could dare take up, he was busy and returned only a few months before his death from a study-stay taken for that purpose in London.

The ghastly accident on the evening of Good-Friday, the 8th of April 1898 at the time of his ferry-journey prepared end to his life dedicated to the service of science, and it can perhaps be never fully explained, since the experienced rower took alone the fatal boat-trip from Lindau on the Bodensee (Lake Constance) and the dead body could not be recovered as yet. Still, according to all circumstances which have become known, perhaps the speculation of Prof. Kägi in his obituary on Bühler is the most plausible that one of the two rudders which was found on the lake, on the next day, driving, might have been carried off by a steamer-wave, and in an attempt to hold it, he might have been drowned in the lake. It is also possible, as was told to me on that place, that the unsteady boat brought to the loss of balance through the act of standing up (on account of the pre-season and the holiday at the time of the beginning of his boat-travel no choice on messenger was at the disposal) or after many hours of strenuous rowing stroke apoplectic fit might have hit him, because he was prone to Apoplexy. He had never been more rich in outlining and work-planning than exactly in the last period. Thus ardently he agitated for new excavations in India, for which he had submitted already in 1895 a well-informed plan characterized by Sinclair as "eminently practical" to the R. Asiatic Society in London. Just six weeks before his death, as a member of the international committee for the research of India formed at Paris Congress in 1897, he made a visit in best disposition to Dr. Pfungst in Frankfurt in order to cause him for the entry to that and for journalistic representation of the purpose. For the excavations he intended to travel personally towards India, as he had already planned. In addition to the Grundriss, epigraphical and other

works also made him busy; thus he thought about continuation of his "Indian Studies" which should discuss the much ventilated question about the age of caste-system on the basis of inscriptional data. On the basis of his fabulous robustness one could predict for him a high lifetime, like his [19] father who had reached and preceded him only a few years in death, and full materialization of his plans. It is, however, not only an interruption of his scientific enterprises what we mourn for. The seed sown in word and writing by him is sprouted up and the further continuation of his last and greatest work, of *Grundriss*, is ensured in accordance with human discretion. The most painful will be that his impressive personality which formed a living mediation between the old respectable tradition of the Śāstrīs and the critical antiquity-related research of the European scholars, his scientific enthusiasm, his honest character, his shining scholastic talent, and his never tiring kindness towards the friends and colleagues will be missed. In spite of his superior knowledge all show of scholarship used to lie far away from him. As an agreeable causeur and witty companion he knew to narrate fascinatingly about his Indian adventures in hunting, as also that what he had explored in the contacts with the Pandits, knew humorous rhyme of his compatriot Busch, equally good so many Sanskrit verses by heart, and knew them to recite in their particular song-like intonation, had contacts with learned Hindus equally actively as with his European colleagues, and was equally respected and popular among his English employers, who attended to his expert advice happily as later with the several Austrian Education-ministers under whom he served. He obtained a special credit also through the cultivation of German connections with India while he was eager to cause his as many as possible fellow countrymen for the travels towards India, to create positions for them through his influence, and to let their works be printed in India. Therefore, he wrote mostly not only in English just as in connection with Wiener Akademie also, in spite of the statutory decisions, succeeded his essays in English language the lingua franca of India as he called it, to be able to publish and used Devanāgarī-alphabets for Sanskrit, not the Latin transcription, but also exhorted even his friends and students to proceed similarly. He wanted to work on India from Wien also and perceived in the European Sanskritists "Missionaries of Science towards India" (Letters to Leumann, 1890), as he tried to receive the modern representatives of the Sanskrit scholarship in India and in general with the India of the present day, teaching so much for the Indian Archäosophy. May be that many times he had gone too far in his eagerness for Indian tradition for the weaknesses of which

he was not blind, still the result has proved the correctness of his method, and the path which he has shown must be further followed.

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- Bombay Sanskrit Series. (Sanskrit Classics for the Use of High Schools and Colleges.) ed. with Notes, by G. BÜHLER. Bombay:
- No. I, Pañchatantra IV and V, 1868. 84, 16 Pp. 8. (4th ed. 1891. 83 Pp. 8.)
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- Āpastamba's Dharmasūtra. Aphorisms on the Sacred Law of the Hindus, by Āpastamba. ed., with a Translation and Notes, by G. BÜHLER, By Order of the Government of Bombay.
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- Part II. Containing Extracts from the Sanskrit Commentary of Haradatta, called Ujjvalā, together with a Sanskrit Index. Bombay 1891. 8, 154 Pp. Gr. 8. (2nd ed. Bombay 1894, together with a Verbal Index to the Sūtras, by TH. BLOCH. 163 Pp. Gr. 8. Bombay S. S. L.)
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- A Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts contained in the Private Libraries of Gujarat, Kāthiāvād, Kachchh, Sindh, and Khāndeś
Fascicle I. Compiled under the superintendence of G. BÜHLER. By Order of Government. Bombay 1871. IX, 245 Pp. 8.

¹ Abbreviations in general as in the "Orientalische Bibliographie"

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